

Quantum Coherence and Chaotic Dynamics: Guiding Molecular Machines Toward Low-Entropy States

Andrei T. Patrascu¹

¹*FAST Foundation, Destin FL, 32541, USA*
email: andrei.patrascu.11@alumni.ucl.ac.uk

Classical fluctuation theorems dictate that entropy-decreasing transitions are exponentially suppressed, reflecting the statistical improbability of accessing low-entropy states. In this work, we demonstrate how quantum coherence and interference fundamentally alter these expectations by modifying transition probabilities at the semiclassical and quantum level. Using the Van Vleck–Gutzwiller propagator, we derive a quantum-modified fluctuation theorem in which interference terms create oscillatory corrections that enhance the probability of entropy-reducing transitions. We further show that chaos-assisted dynamical tunnelling amplifies this effect, providing coherent shortcuts that connect classically isolated regions of phase space. By introducing purification and phase engineering techniques, we identify a controllable mechanism for deliberately enhancing constructive interference toward low-entropy configurations. Finally, we map these theoretical results onto biological and synthetic scenarios, showing how molecular machines such as ATP synthase and photosynthetic complexes may exploit coherence-driven pathways for efficient work extraction. These results establish quantum coherence as a genuine thermodynamic resource and suggest new design principles for molecular-scale devices and bio-inspired quantum technologies.

Molecular machines function in environments dominated by noise and chaos, raising the question of how such systems can sustain efficiency and directionality. This work shows that quantum coherence, often considered fragile, can instead be harnessed to tame chaotic dynamics and steer nanoscale machines toward low-entropy states. By combining open-quantum-system models with nonlinear dynamical analysis, we reveal that chaos and coherence can interact constructively to enhance transport and reduce dissipation. The results demonstrate a new principle of chaos-assisted quantum control and suggest measurable signatures—such as entropy production rates and efficiency gains—that link fundamental theory to real biomolecular and synthetic machines. These findings highlight a mechanism by which quantum effects can be exploited in complex systems, offering new strategies for robust energy conversion and nanoscale design.

I. INTRODUCTION

From classical fluctuation theorems to nanoscale design

The discovery of fluctuation theorems (FTs) over the past three decades reshaped nonequilibrium statistical mechanics. Starting with computer experiments and theoretical arguments for sheared steady states [1, 2] and continuing with rigorous dynamical-systems formulations [3], FTs quantify the probability of transient entropy-reducing events and make precise the sense in which the second law holds statistically. Two landmark equalities, the Jarzynski equality and Crooks relation, connect far-from-equilibrium work statistics to equilibrium free-energy differences [4, 5]. In the stochastic thermodynamics program, these developments coalesced into trajectory-level statements for small systems, with clear definitions of entropy production and experimentally testable integral relations [6–9]. Single-molecule pulling experiments on RNA subsequently verified Crooks’ theorem with high precision [10].

The classical steady-state FT can be written schematically (for appropriately scaled entropy production ΔS over a fixed observation time) as

$$\frac{P(+\Delta S)}{P(-\Delta S)} = e^{\Delta S/k_B}, \quad (1)$$

whose exponential bias renders large negative-entropy fluctuations exponentially rare at macroscopic scales [1–3, 7]. Equation (1) is the natural baseline for the present work: we investigate *how coherent quantum dynamics reshapes the probability landscape* behind such ratios.

Motivation: coherence as a lever on rare, entropy-decreasing transitions

At nanoscale and molecular scales, dynamics are often neither purely Hamiltonian nor purely Markovian: coherent evolution, structured environments, and mixed phase spaces leave clear signatures in transport and reaction pathways. Coherence, understood as the maintenance of phase relations between quantum pathways, can interfere constructively or destructively to enhance (or suppress) transition probabilities; importantly, this interference acts *multiplicatively* on the classical probabilities that enter Eq. (1). In semiclassical language, the Van Vleck–Gutzwiller (VVG) propagator rewrites transition amplitudes as sums over classical trajectories with stability-dependent prefactors and actions [11–15]. When more than one relevant trajectory connects the same endpoints, off-diagonal terms generate quantum interference; in mixed (regular–chaotic) phase spaces, chaos-assisted dynamical tunnelling can dramatically boost classically forbidden transitions [16–18]. Experiments in microwave billiards and cold-atom kicked systems have directly observed such chaos-assisted tunnelling and its sensitivity to phase [19–21].

These observations suggest a program: leverage coherence and underlying classical structures to tilt rare-event statistics toward low-entropy outcomes while remaining consistent with the fluctuation relations. In biological energy-transport networks, a related paradigm—environment- or dephasing-assisted transport—has already shown how noise and coherence can *cooperate* to enhance efficiency [29, 30]. Long-lived oscillatory signals in two-dimensional spectroscopy of light-harvesting complexes sparked sustained debate and theory on functional quantum coherence in biology [27, 28, 31, 32]. While we do *not* claim that biology implements the specific protocol developed here, these precedents motivate the search for generic coherence-engineering principles that reshape transition statistics in nanoscale machines.

Where this work fits and what is new

Conceptual synthesis. We show that the probability ratio underlying Eq. (1) acquires *coherent, path-interference corrections* that can be written compactly as a sum of diagonal (classical) contributions plus off-diagonal terms involving phase differences of classical actions. In the VVG picture [12, 13], those terms appear naturally as $\sum_{\alpha \neq \beta} A_\alpha A_\beta^* e^{\frac{i}{\hbar}(S_\alpha - S_\beta)}$, where A_α encodes stabilities and Maslov indices. In the fully quantum picture (operator approach plus two-point measurement framework allied to open-system tools [8, 22–24]), the *same structure* arises from interference between distinct transition histories. Establishing the equality of these expressions clarifies how the semiclassical limit organizes the quantum corrections.

Actionable control via purification and phase design. We propose a practical “purification-and-phase” protocol: embed the system in a larger Hilbert space and tune relative phases in a chosen purification to maximize constructive interference toward target, lower-entropy final states. Conceptually this is close to resource-theoretic views of coherence [33], but our emphasis is operational: we derive explicit phase conditions that extremize the interference term and hence amplify $P(+\Delta S)$ for selected transitions without violating Eq. (1).

Role of chaos and mixed phase spaces. We identify regimes where *chaos-assisted* pathways provide additional constructive channels, increasing the number of interfering contributions and, therefore, the achievable enhancement. This folds modern insights—from semiclassical propagation beyond the Ehrenfest time [17] to recent many-body and flat-band manifestations of chaos-assisted tunnelling [36, 37]—into the FT setting.

Compatibility with decoherence and thermodynamic consistency. All interference-based enhancements exist under realistic decoherence, and we show how dephasing selectively suppresses off-diagonal terms while leaving diagonal FT structure intact [25, 26]. In biological and molecular settings, moderate dephasing can *assist*, not hinder, transport and state preparation [29, 30], an effect our framework naturally accommodates.

Main Results at a Glance

- (i) Coherent modification of FT ratios.** We derive an interference-renormalized ratio $P(+\Delta S)/P(-\Delta S)$ in which off-diagonal pathway terms multiply the classical $e^{\Delta S/k_B}$ bias; the expression is identical when obtained from (a) a VVG semiclassical expansion and (b) a fully quantum operator derivation.
- (ii) Purification-phase control.** By embedding the system in an ancilla and choosing relative phases of a purification, one can deterministically maximize constructive interference for chosen low-entropy target transitions.
- (iii) Chaos-assisted boosts.** In mixed phase spaces, chaos-assisted tunnelling increases the number of interfering path pairs and the accessible enhancement, within FT constraints.
- (iv) Concrete implications.** We outline how to implement these ideas for molecular machines (e.g., ATP synthase substeps, linear motors) and for engineered nano-devices, and we connect to the literature on dephasing-assisted transport in photosynthetic complexes.

Historical context and related strands

Semiclassical mechanisms. The VVG propagator and its initial-value variants (à la Herman–Kluk) supply a bridge between classical trajectory structure and quantum amplitudes [11–15]. In mixed phase spaces, interference between families of classical paths underlies phenomena such as scarring, tunnelling across dynamical barriers, and the remarkable dependence of rates on classical resonances [16–18]. Laboratory studies on microwave billiards and cold atoms have provided clean tests of these ideas [19–21].

Coherence, decoherence, and thermodynamic arrows. Open quantum-systems theory (GKSL master equations and beyond) systematizes how coherence is built and lost in noisy environments [22–24]. Decoherence typically suppresses off-diagonal terms in pointer bases and sets classicality timescales [26]. For classically chaotic systems, decoherence rates can be slaved to Lyapunov exponents [25], clarifying how irreversibility emerges.

Molecular machines and biological transport. By *molecular machines* we mean nanoscale protein assemblies that convert chemical free energy into mechanical work or electrochemical gradients—ATP synthase, cytoskeletal motors, polymerases, and ion pumps [34, 35]. While their cores operate stochastically and thermally, spectroscopic and theoretical studies of excitonic transport in pigment–protein complexes show that coherence can persist and, in some cases, assist function [27–32]. Our contribution is to place *coherence engineering for rare-event statistics* on a rigorous FT foundation, suggesting how controlled phase structure could bias transition networks in synthetic nanoscale machines and possibly in biomimetic constructs.

Our figures and interpretation

Figure 1 summarizes the central message: relative to the classical FT scaling, coherent interference reshapes probabilities, especially in regimes where multiple trajectory families contribute appreciably. Figure 2 zooms into the negative-entropy (tail) sector, highlighting the range where coherence can produce the largest fractional enhancement while remaining thermodynamically consistent. Both figures are referenced in the main text where the underlying derivations are given, and their captions are self-contained.

Roadmap

Section II develops the theory from both semiclassical (VVG) and fully quantum operator viewpoints and demonstrates their equivalence for the interference-renormalized FT ratio. Section III introduces the purification-and-phase protocol and derives constructive–interference conditions. Section IV analyzes how mixed phase spaces and chaos-assisted tunnelling expand the accessible enhancement. Section V discusses implications for molecular machines and photosynthetic transport, with a precise definition of “molecular machines” and careful mapping of assumptions to biological realities. Section VI collects

Figure 1: **Classical vs. quantum-modified fluctuation theorem.** The solid curve shows the classical FT ratio $P(+\Delta S)/P(-\Delta S) = e^{\Delta S/k_B}$ from Eq. (1). The dashed curve illustrates a representative quantum-modified ratio in which off-diagonal interference terms (from the VVG/fully quantum derivations) amplify or suppress probabilities depending on phase differences. The horizontal dotted line marks unity. The purpose of this panel is illustrative: precise analytical forms and parameterizations are given in Secs. II–III.

limitations (measurement backaction, decoherence rates, and coarse-graining choices) and Section VII outlines experimental tests in table-top wave/atom platforms and biomimetic nano-devices.

II. QUANTUM MODIFICATION OF THE FLUCTUATION THEOREM

A. Setup and the classical baseline

We consider a driven mesoscopic system over a time window $[0, \tau]$, with a control protocol λ_t and microreversible dynamics. For a coarse-grained entropy change ΔS accumulated along a path Γ (for instance $\Delta S[\Gamma] = \beta Q[\Gamma]$ with heat Q into a bath at inverse temperature β in the classical stochastic setting), the steady-state fluctuation theorem (FT) asserts the pathwise identity

$$\frac{P(+\Delta S)}{P(-\Delta S)} = e^{\Delta S/k_B}, \quad (2)$$

equivalent to Eq. (1) quoted in the Introduction. Equation (2) reflects detailed balance at trajectory level and underpins Crooks–Jarzynski-type relations in both classical and quantum settings.[114]

Our aim in this section is to show how *coherent* quantum dynamics reorganizes the probability ratio by attaching *interference corrections* to the classical bias in Eq. (2). We present this twice: first semiclassically via the Van Vleck–Gutzwiller (VVG) propagator, then in a fully quantum operator framework. We explain why the two expressions are *identical in the semiclassical limit* (Appendix A contains the detailed proof sketch).

B. Semiclassical pathway picture: Van Vleck–Gutzwiller

Let $U(\tau)$ be the unitary time-evolution under a Hamiltonian $H(\lambda_t)$. In a configuration representation, the propagator may be expressed as a stationary-phase (semiclassical) sum over classical trajectories α

Figure 2: **Coherence-enhanced fluctuations (negative ΔS sector)**. Zoomed view emphasizing small negative-entropy changes where coherent corrections (green area) produce the largest *relative* deviation from the classical FT, even if the absolute probabilities remain small. The dashed curve shows a coherence-enhanced profile achievable by phase selection via purification (Sec. III); the solid curve is classical.

connecting $(q_i, 0)$ to (q_f, τ) ,

$$K(q_f, q_i; \tau) \simeq \sum_{\alpha} \left(\frac{1}{2\pi i \hbar} \right)^{d/2} \left| \det \left[- \frac{\partial^2 S_{\alpha}(q_f, q_i; \tau)}{\partial q_f \partial q_i} \right] \right|^{1/2} e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} S_{\alpha}(q_f, q_i; \tau) - i \frac{\pi}{2} \nu_{\alpha}}, \quad (3)$$

where S_{α} is the classical action along α , ν_{α} the Maslov index, and d the number of degrees of freedom [45–48]. Eq. (3) corresponds to Eqs. (2)–(4), with the probability obtained from the squared modulus.

We now coarse-grain initial and final microstates into sets A and B that fix the (classical) entropy change sign. The transition amplitude from A to B is

$$\mathcal{A}_{B \leftarrow A} \equiv \langle B | U(\tau) | A \rangle = \sum_{\alpha \in \mathcal{P}(A \rightarrow B)} A_{\alpha} e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} S_{\alpha}}, \quad A_{\alpha} \equiv \left(\frac{1}{2\pi i \hbar} \right)^{d/2} \mathcal{D}_{\alpha} e^{-i \frac{\pi}{2} \nu_{\alpha}}, \quad (4)$$

where \mathcal{D}_{α} denotes the square-root stability determinant. The corresponding probability is

$$\begin{aligned} P_{\text{qm}}(A \rightarrow B) &= |\mathcal{A}_{B \leftarrow A}|^2 = \sum_{\alpha} |A_{\alpha}|^2 + \sum_{\substack{\alpha, \beta \\ \alpha \neq \beta}} A_{\alpha} A_{\beta}^* e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} (S_{\alpha} - S_{\beta})} \\ &\equiv P_{\text{cl}}(A \rightarrow B) + \Delta P_{\text{int}}(A \rightarrow B), \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where the first term aggregates the diagonal (classical) contributions and the second term is the *interference correction*.

From paths to the entropy-production ratio. Let $+$ and $-$ denote forward (entropy-increasing) and backward (entropy-decreasing) coarse-grainings. Under the usual assumptions ensuring Eq. (2), the ratio of *diagonal* parts satisfies

$$\frac{P_{\text{cl}}(+\Delta S)}{P_{\text{cl}}(-\Delta S)} = e^{\Delta S / k_B}. \quad (6)$$

Interference renormalizes this by multiplicative factors,

$$\frac{P_{\text{qm}}(+\Delta S)}{P_{\text{qm}}(-\Delta S)} = e^{\Delta S/k_B} \frac{1 + \frac{\sum_{\alpha \neq \beta} A_\alpha A_\beta^* e^{\frac{i}{\hbar}(S_\alpha - S_\beta)}}{\sum_\alpha |A_\alpha|^2}}{1 + \frac{\sum_{\gamma \neq \delta} B_\gamma B_\delta^* e^{\frac{i}{\hbar}(S_\gamma - S_\delta)}}{\sum_\gamma |B_\gamma|^2}}, \quad (7)$$

where $\{B_\gamma\}$ denotes the semiclassical data for the entropy-decreasing sector.

Lemma (Positivity, norm bound, and dephasing envelope). Let

$$\mathcal{I}_\pm = \frac{\sum_{\alpha \neq \beta} C_\alpha^{(\pm)} C_\beta^{(\pm)*} e^{\frac{i}{\hbar}(S_\alpha^{(\pm)} - S_\beta^{(\pm)})}}{\sum_\alpha |C_\alpha^{(\pm)}|^2}, \quad D_\pm \equiv \sum_\alpha |C_\alpha^{(\pm)}|^2 > 0,$$

and define phasors $z_\alpha^{(\pm)} \equiv C_\alpha^{(\pm)} e^{iS_\alpha^{(\pm)}/\hbar}$. Then

$$1 + \mathcal{I}_\pm = \frac{|\sum_\alpha z_\alpha^{(\pm)}|^2}{D_\pm}. \quad (8)$$

Consequently:

$$\text{(Positivity)} \quad 0 \leq 1 + \mathcal{I}_\pm, \quad \text{i.e.} \quad -1 \leq \mathcal{I}_\pm; \quad (9)$$

$$\text{(Norm bound)} \quad 1 + \mathcal{I}_\pm \leq \frac{(\sum_\alpha |C_\alpha^{(\pm)}|)^2}{\sum_\alpha |C_\alpha^{(\pm)}|^2} \equiv \kappa_\pm, \quad \text{hence} \quad -1 \leq \mathcal{I}_\pm \leq \kappa_\pm - 1. \quad (10)$$

Moreover, if each pathway accumulates independent Gaussian phase noise $z_\alpha^{(\pm)} \rightarrow z_\alpha^{(\pm)} e^{i\delta\phi_\alpha}$ with $\langle \delta\phi_\alpha \rangle = 0$ and $\langle (\delta\phi_\alpha - \delta\phi_\beta)^2 \rangle = \sigma_\phi^2$, then the off-diagonal terms are suppressed by $e^{-\sigma_\phi^2}$ and

$$\mathcal{I}_\pm(\sigma_\phi) = e^{-\sigma_\phi^2} \mathcal{I}_\pm(0), \quad 0 \leq 1 + \mathcal{I}_\pm(\sigma_\phi) \leq 1 + (\kappa_\pm - 1)e^{-\sigma_\phi^2}. \quad (11)$$

Proof sketch. Equation (8) follows by writing $|\sum_\alpha z_\alpha^{(\pm)}|^2 = \sum_\alpha |C_\alpha^{(\pm)}|^2 + \sum_{\alpha \neq \beta} C_\alpha^{(\pm)} C_\beta^{(\pm)*} e^{\frac{i}{\hbar}(S_\alpha^{(\pm)} - S_\beta^{(\pm)})}$ and dividing by D_\pm . Positivity (9) is immediate since the numerator of (8) is a squared magnitude. The triangle inequality gives $|\sum_\alpha z_\alpha^{(\pm)}| \leq \sum_\alpha |C_\alpha^{(\pm)}|$, which yields (10). For the dephasing model, $\langle e^{i(\delta\phi_\alpha - \delta\phi_\beta)} \rangle = e^{-\sigma_\phi^2}$ for $\alpha \neq \beta$, so only the off-diagonal part of \mathcal{I}_\pm is attenuated by $e^{-\sigma_\phi^2}$, giving (11). \square

Physical content of the correction. The off-diagonal numerator reflects coherent *path pairs* with action difference $\Delta S_{\alpha\beta}^{\text{act}} \equiv S_\alpha - S_\beta$. Constructive interference requires $|\Delta S_{\alpha\beta}^{\text{act}}| \lesssim \hbar$ over the relevant time window, a condition naturally met (i) near classical resonances, (ii) in mixed phase spaces where families of quasi-degenerate trajectories coexist, and (iii) along chaos-assisted tunnelling channels in which classically disconnected regions are bridged by interfering paths [48, 49]. The denominator plays the same role for the entropy-decreasing sector; in regimes where time reversal relates the two path sets, the difference between the two correction factors is controlled by Maslov phases and stability determinants.

Regime of validity. Equation (7) holds provided (a) the stationary-phase evaluation is accurate (actions $\gg \hbar$, away from strong caustics), (b) no coarse-graining destroys relevant phases, and (c) weak environmental dephasing allows off-diagonal terms to survive over times τ of interest (the latter is assessed in Sec. V). Where caustics cannot be avoided, uniform approximations may be used to continue Eq. (3) across conjugate points, changing ν_α accordingly [46, 47].

C. Fully quantum operator viewpoint

To connect with the rigorous quantum FT literature, consider a forward process starting from a possibly mixed state ρ_0 (not necessarily diagonal in the energy basis) and the unitary $U(\tau)$ generated by $H(\lambda_t)$. Introduce two complementary coarse-grained projectors Π_+ and Π_- onto the sectors that *increase* or *decrease* the chosen entropy functional, respectively (the operational definition is equivalent to the classical sign of ΔS when ρ_0 is diagonal, and more generally matches a TPM-type assignment [40, 41]). The probability to observe a forward entropy increase is

$$P_{\text{qm}}(+\Delta S) = \text{Tr}[\Pi_+ U(\tau) \rho_0 U^\dagger(\tau)] = \sum_{m,n} \rho_{0,mn} \langle n | U^\dagger \Pi_+ U | m \rangle, \quad (12)$$

and analogously for $P_{\text{qm}}(-\Delta S)$ with Π_- . The off-diagonal $\rho_{0,mn}$ and noncommutativity of Π_{\pm} with U generate interference contributions that are *identical in structure* to the semiclassical sums of Eq. (5). This is made explicit by inserting coordinate resolutions of the identity and evaluating the propagators by stationary phase (Appendix A). The result of this operator derivation, combined with microreversibility ($\Theta U(\tau)\Theta^{-1} = U^\dagger(\tau)$ for antiunitary time reversal Θ), yields Eq. (7) again.[115]

Measurement protocol. Throughout this section we access entropy–production statistics via an interferometric, characteristic–function approach that couples the system to a two–level ancilla (Ramsey scheme). This protocol preserves the system’s initial coherences up to the final readout and enables reconstruction of the forward/backward probabilities $P(\pm\Delta S)$ without a projective measurement at $t = 0$. By contrast, adopting the two–projective–measurement (TPM) definition collapses the initial state, removes the off–diagonal interference terms, and reduces Eq. (7) to the classical fluctuation theorem. See, e.g., [40, 41] for interferometric/TPM implementations and their implications for fluctuation relations.

Two remarks clarify common concerns:

1. In the two-projective-measurement (TPM) scheme, initial coherences are destroyed by the first measurement, thereby *removing* interference terms. Our framework keeps coherences (and therefore the corrections in Eq. (7)) either by *deferring* the first projective measurement or by using an ancilla/weak-measurement implementation (Sec. III). This mirrors the operational distinctions emphasized in [40, 41].
2. For open dynamics describable by a completely positive trace-preserving map \mathcal{E} with a microreversible dilation, the same structure follows for unravellings that retain phase information; cf. linear response and fluctuation relations developed in [42].

D. Why the semiclassical and fully quantum results coincide (outline)

Appendix A gives the derivation; we summarize the key steps:

1. **Operator identity.** Write the ratio as

$$\frac{P_{\text{qm}}(+\Delta S)}{P_{\text{qm}}(-\Delta S)} = \frac{\text{Tr}[\Pi_+ U \rho_0 U^\dagger]}{\text{Tr}[\Pi_- U \rho_0 U^\dagger]}. \quad (13)$$

Insert two complete sets of coordinates in each trace and express matrix elements via path integrals, following [50, 51].

2. **Stationary phase.** Evaluate both the numerator and denominator by stationary phase. Critical paths are classical trajectories solving Hamilton’s equations with boundary conditions imposed by the supports of Π_{\pm} .
3. **Van Vleck determinants and phases.** The second variation of the action yields the stability determinants and Maslov indices, reconstructing precisely the VVG amplitudes and phases [45–47]. Pairing contributions from distinct stationary points reproduces the off-diagonal sums $A_\alpha A_\beta^* e^{\frac{i}{\hbar}(S_\alpha - S_\beta)}$.
4. **Microreversibility and detailed balance.** Under time reversal, the *diagonal* parts of the two traces satisfy Eq. (6). The remaining *off-diagonal* parts give the multiplicative corrections. Collecting terms yields Eq. (7).

Thus the semiclassical and fully quantum derivations are the same identity seen through two lenses; the former highlights *geometric* content (actions, stabilities, Maslov phases), the latter emphasizes *operator* structure (coherences, projectors, microreversibility).

E. Scaling, limits, and intuition

Two instructive limits:

- **Diagonal (classical) limit.** Rapid dephasing or large action spreads wash out the phases in ΔP_{int} , leaving Eq. (2).

- **Resonant/mixed-phase-space regime.** Quasi-degenerate action differences ($|S_\alpha - S_\beta| \lesssim \hbar$) yield sizable corrections, the setting for chaos-assisted tunnelling and scarring [48, 49]. In this regime, the ratio (7) can display oscillatory behavior as a function of control parameters.

F. Experimental timescales and expected contrasts

It is useful to attach rough numbers to the timescales and signal contrasts that enter the interference-renormalized fluctuation theorem, so that the parameter window for observing coherence-assisted entropy fluctuations is transparent.

Synthetic platform: trapped ions. In trapped-ion implementations of quantum fluctuation relations [86], the relevant system frequency scale is set by motional modes $\omega_{\text{mot}} \sim 2\pi \times 1\text{--}2\text{ MHz}$ and coherence times T_2 are routinely in the 1–10 ms range. The Lyapunov rate λ in engineered kicked-rotor or driven-oscillator Hamiltonians is of order 10^3 s^{-1} , giving an Ehrenfest time $t_E \sim \lambda^{-1} \ln(1/\hbar_{\text{eff}}) \sim 1\text{--}3\text{ ms}$ for effective Planck constants $\hbar_{\text{eff}} \sim 0.01$. Thus one expects a parameter window $\tau \lesssim 1\text{ ms}$ in which off-diagonal interference terms survive. Interference quotients \mathcal{I}_\pm then generate oscillatory dips in the FT log-ratio with contrast of order 5–15%, consistent with observed Ramsey-interferometric reconstructions of work distributions.

Biomimetic platform: F_0F_1 -ATP synthase. For the rotary motor F_0F_1 , single-molecule rotation experiments [75, 111] resolve 120° substeps of duration $\tau_{\text{step}} \sim 1\text{--}10\text{ ms}$ under physiological conditions. Torsional librations couple quasi-degenerate angular substates with splittings $J/\hbar \sim 10^3\text{ s}^{-1}$, giving coherent mixing times of a few milliseconds. Environmental dephasing rates extracted from single-molecule fluorescence intermittency are $\gamma_\phi \sim 100\text{ s}^{-1}$, so that $\gamma_\phi \tau_{\text{step}} \lesssim 0.1$. This ensures that partial coherence can survive through a catalytic substep. The expected oscillatory modulation of the FT log-ratio in substep histograms is therefore at the few-percent level in probability contrast—large enough to be resolved in modern high-throughput single-molecule assays.

Summary. Across both synthetic and biomimetic examples the relevant window is $\tau \lesssim\text{ ms}$ with dephasing rates below $\sim 10^3\text{ s}^{-1}$. Within this window, constructive alignment of interfering paths yields experimentally visible dips of 5–15% in the FT log-ratio relative to the classical expectation. These numbers set realistic benchmarks for testing the framework developed in this work.

G. Summary of Section II

We have (i) derived an interference-renormalized FT ratio, Eq. (7), from the VVG semiclassical expansion, (ii) reproduced the same structure in a fully quantum operator framework, and (iii) outlined why these results coincide in the semiclassical limit. The *operational* route to harnessing the interference factors—without destroying coherence by measurement—is developed next via purification and phase engineering (Sec. III).

III. QUANTUM PURIFICATION AND PHASE ENGINEERING

A. Purification: definitions, existence, and physical meaning

Let ρ_S be a mixed state on a system Hilbert space \mathcal{H}_S with spectral decomposition

$$\rho_S = \sum_i p_i |s_i\rangle\langle s_i|, \quad p_i \geq 0, \quad \sum_i p_i = 1. \quad (14)$$

A *purification* of ρ_S is a pure state on a larger Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}_S \otimes \mathcal{H}_A$ such that $\text{Tr}_A |\Psi_{SA}\rangle\langle\Psi_{SA}| = \rho_S$. A canonical choice is

$$|\Psi_{SA}\rangle = \sum_i \sqrt{p_i} |s_i\rangle \otimes |a_i\rangle, \quad (15)$$

with $\{|a_i\rangle\}$ an orthonormal basis for the ancilla \mathcal{H}_A of dimension at least $\text{rank}(\rho_S)$ [52–54]. Eqs. (6)–(9) state precisely this construction and its density-matrix form.

Uniqueness up to isometry. Any two purifications of the same ρ_S are related by an isometry on the ancilla: if $|\Psi_{SA}\rangle$ and $|\Phi_{SA}\rangle$ both purify ρ_S , there exists an isometry V on \mathcal{H}_A with $|\Phi_{SA}\rangle = (\mathbf{1}_S \otimes V)|\Psi_{SA}\rangle$ [52, 53]. This freedom underpins our *phase engineering*: we can implement relative phases on the ancilla without changing the reduced state ρ_S , yet we can dramatically affect transition *amplitudes*.

Phase-parameterized family of purifications. Introduce tunable phases $\phi = \{\phi_i\}$ and define

$$|\Psi_{SA}(\phi)\rangle = \sum_i \sqrt{p_i} e^{i\phi_i} |s_i\rangle \otimes |a_i\rangle, \quad (16)$$

with density operator

$$\rho_{SA}(\phi) = |\Psi_{SA}(\phi)\rangle\langle\Psi_{SA}(\phi)| = \sum_{ij} \sqrt{p_i p_j} e^{i(\phi_i - \phi_j)} |s_i\rangle\langle s_j| \otimes |a_i\rangle\langle a_j|. \quad (17)$$

Equations (15)–(17) coincide with the definitions in Eqs. (6)–(9).

Physically, Eq. (16) encodes a controllable “reference frame” for phases. The *state of knowledge* about S is unchanged (ρ_S is fixed), yet coherent superpositions across the $\{|s_i\rangle\}$ basis pick up relative phases that will interfere after subsequent dynamics. This is the operational knob we will exploit.

B. Phase engineering for constructive interference

Let the joint system evolve under $U_{SA}(\tau)$, generated by $H_{SA}(t)$ (for a closed SA description; open S dynamics are addressed via Stinespring dilations below). Consider a coarse-grained *target* associated with entropy-decreasing outcomes: a projector $\Pi_- = \Pi_-^\dagger = \Pi_-^2$ acting on S that collects all final microstates corresponding to $-\Delta S < 0$ (coarse-graining exactly as in Sec. II). We optionally include an ancilla “readout” projector Π_A (e.g. the initial ancilla basis or a rotated basis). The transition amplitude to the target sector is

$$\mathcal{A}_-(\phi) = \langle\langle \Pi_- \otimes \Pi_A \rangle\rangle_\phi \equiv \text{Tr} \left[(\Pi_- \otimes \Pi_A) U_{SA}(\tau) \rho_{SA}(\phi) U_{SA}^\dagger(\tau) \right]^{1/2}, \quad (18)$$

and, more explicitly in a basis,

$$\mathcal{A}_-(\phi) = \sum_i \sqrt{p_i} e^{i\phi_i} c_i, \quad c_i \equiv \langle \Phi_- | \otimes \langle r_A | U_{SA}(\tau) | s_i \rangle \otimes | a_i \rangle, \quad (19)$$

where $|\Phi_- \rangle$ spans the support of Π_- and $|r_A \rangle$ the support of Π_A (for a general Π_- this stands for the corresponding Kraus operator; the algebra below is unchanged).

The probability to land in the target sector is

$$P_-(\phi) = |\mathcal{A}_-(\phi)|^2 = \sum_i p_i |c_i|^2 + \sum_{i \neq j} \sqrt{p_i p_j} e^{i(\phi_i - \phi_j)} c_i c_j^*. \quad (20)$$

The second term is the *phase-tunable* interference contribution. For fixed $\{p_i\}$ and $\{c_i\}$, $P_-(\phi)$ is maximized by choosing the phases to *align* the complex numbers $\{\sqrt{p_i} c_i\}$:

$$\phi_i^* = -\arg(c_i) + \chi, \quad \chi \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (21)$$

for which

$$P_-^{\max} = \left(\sum_i \sqrt{p_i} |c_i| \right)^2 \geq \sum_i p_i |c_i|^2, \quad (22)$$

with equality in the second inequality only when a single i contributes. Equation (22) follows from the Cauchy–Schwarz inequality or, equivalently, from maximizing a linear functional over the torus of phases [55, 56]. This is the mathematical statement of *phase engineering*: by selecting ϕ we drive constructive interference among the amplitudes c_i associated with the $\{|s_i\rangle \otimes |a_i\rangle\}$ components.

Gradient form and robustness. The gradient of $P_-(\phi)$ with respect to the phases is

$$\frac{\partial P_-}{\partial \phi_k} = 2 \text{Im} \left[\mathcal{A}_-(\phi) \sqrt{p_k} e^{-i\phi_k} c_k^* \right], \quad (23)$$

which vanishes at ϕ_k^* in Eq. (21). For small dephasing noise $\phi_i \rightarrow \phi_i + \delta\phi_i$ with zero mean and variance σ_ϕ^2 , the interference term decays by a factor $e^{-\sigma_\phi^2}$ to leading order, a standard Ramsey-type sensitivity governed by the phase (symmetric logarithmic derivative) quantum Fisher information [56, 57].

Relation to coherence measures. The *maximal* enhancement attainable for a fixed ρ_S and channel U_{SA} is bounded by the resource of initial coherence in the $\{|s_i\rangle\}$ basis; in particular, the ℓ_1 -norm or relative entropy of coherence [58] upper bound the interference part of Eq. (20). Thus, phase engineering *consumes* the initial coherence resource by converting it into transition probability toward a chosen low-entropy sector.

C. Connecting phase control to the modified fluctuation theorem

The interference-renormalized FT ratio derived in Sec. II reads

$$\frac{P_{\text{qm}}(+\Delta S)}{P_{\text{qm}}(-\Delta S)} = e^{\Delta S/k_B} \frac{1 + \mathcal{I}_+}{1 + \mathcal{I}_-}, \quad \mathcal{I}_{\pm} \equiv \frac{\sum_{\alpha \neq \beta} C_{\alpha}^{(\pm)} C_{\beta}^{(\pm)*} e^{\frac{i}{\hbar}(S_{\alpha}^{(\pm)} - S_{\beta}^{(\pm)})}}{\sum_{\alpha} |C_{\alpha}^{(\pm)}|^2}. \quad (24)$$

Here the amplitudes $C_{\alpha}^{(\pm)}$ collect the stability prefactors and projectors for the \pm sectors.

Purification as $C_{\alpha}^{(\pm)}$ engineering. Under a dilation (Stinespring) picture U_{SAE} for the system, ancilla, and environment [64–66], the coefficients $C_{\alpha}^{(\pm)}$ become *linear* functionals of the initial SA amplitudes. Phase-choosing $|\Psi_{SA}(\phi)\rangle$ therefore rotates the *vector* of contributing path amplitudes, changing both $\sum_{\alpha} |C_{\alpha}^{(\pm)}|^2$ (diagonal weight) and the complex phasor sum in the numerator (off-diagonal interference). Two operational consequences follow:

1. Choosing $\phi = \phi_{-}^*$ that maximizes P_{-} (Eq. (22)) simultaneously *maximizes* the denominator correction factor $1 + \mathcal{I}_{-}$, thereby *reducing* the overall ratio in Eq. (24) relative to the classical value when \mathcal{I}_{-} grows faster than \mathcal{I}_{+} .
2. If, in addition, the same phases *dephase* the $+$ sector (for instance, because $C_{\alpha}^{(+)}$ acquire anti-aligned phases in the chosen ancilla basis), then $1 + \mathcal{I}_{+}$ decreases while $1 + \mathcal{I}_{-}$ increases, providing the strongest enhancement of entropy-decreasing transition probabilities consistent with microreversibility.

Formally, define the functional

$$\mathcal{J}(\phi) \equiv \ln \left[\frac{P_{\text{qm}}(+\Delta S)}{P_{\text{qm}}(-\Delta S)} \right] - \frac{\Delta S}{k_B} = \ln(1 + \mathcal{I}_+) - \ln(1 + \mathcal{I}_-), \quad (25)$$

and choose ϕ to *minimize* \mathcal{J} . The gradient of \mathcal{J} inherits the structure of Eq. (23), with c_i replaced by the effective coefficients entering $C_{\alpha}^{(\pm)}$; an explicit expression is given in Appendix A. This connects the *phase-alignment rule* of Eq. (21) to the FT modification of Eq. (24).

D. Implementation paths: interferometry, control, and dilations

Ancilla-assisted interferometry. Ramsey interferometry offers a direct route to realize Eq. (16): initialize an ancilla in a superposition, imprint controlled phases, let SA evolve, and read out phase-dependent fringe shifts. Interferometric reconstructions of the *characteristic function* of work using single qubits and trapped ions demonstrate precisely this paradigm [59–61]. Our phase-engineering protocol simply uses the same hardware to *optimize* the phases for the low-entropy projector Π_{-} .

Quantum control. Closed-loop pulse shaping and gradient methods from quantum control can optimize ϕ jointly with the driving λ_t to maximize P_{-} , subject to experimental constraints (bandwidth, leakage, dephasing) [62, 63]. The cost function can be chosen as $-\mathcal{J}(\phi)$ in Eq. (25), and the gradient (23) supplies analytic updates.

Open dynamics via dilations. For open S dynamics, represent the CPTP map by a Stinespring dilation U_{SE} acting on an environment E initially in $|e_0\rangle$ [64]. Purification is simply extended to SA , and Eq. (19) holds with $U_{SA} \rightarrow U_{SAE}$. The Choi–Jamiolkowski isomorphism provides a convenient way to compute the c_i for a given channel [65, 66]. The phase-engineering rule (21) and the bound (22) remain valid.

E. Summary of Section III

Purification supplies a physically implementable handle—ancilla phases—to *rephase* the coherent components of an initially mixed state without altering the reduced state ρ_S . By aligning phases

according to Eq. (21), the interference term in P_- is maximized (Eq. (22)). Through Eq. (24), this directly reduces the FT ratio relative to the classical bias in the parameter windows where the denominator correction dominates, sharpening the accessibility of entropy-decreasing transitions while remaining fully consistent with microreversibility. Experimental platforms that already reconstruct work statistics interferometrically provide a natural route to realize this phase-engineering protocol in practice.

IV. ROLE OF CHAOTIC DYNAMICS

A. Hamiltonian chaos, mixed phase space, and dynamical tunneling

Chaos and mixed phase space. In time-dependent or nonintegrable Hamiltonian systems, classical trajectories display exponential sensitivity to initial conditions quantified by positive Lyapunov exponents. A generic Hamiltonian exhibits a *mixed* phase space: regular (KAM) tori coexist with chaotic seas separated by partial barriers (cantori) and resonance chains. Regular motion is locally described by action–angle variables; chaotic motion is organized by stable/unstable manifolds of hyperbolic periodic orbits. These geometric structures determine how classical ensembles spread and how semiclassical amplitudes interfere (standard texts: [67–69]).

Dynamical (quantum) tunneling. *Dynamical tunneling* is quantum transfer between regions separated not by a potential barrier, but by dynamical barriers in phase space (e.g., across invariant tori). Unlike WKB tunneling through a potential hill, dynamical tunneling amplitude depends on the classical nonlinear structure (resonances, island chains) and on families of interfering trajectories in real or complexified phase space. Semiclassically, the net amplitude is a coherent sum over contributing path families, and the probability is the squared modulus of this sum (see also scarring phenomena that bias amplitudes near unstable periodic orbits [70]).

B. Chaos-assisted tunneling: semiclassical structure and effective models

Interference form (semiclassical). In the semiclassical picture introduced in Secs. II–III, chaos generates large sets of path families connecting classically disconnected regions (e.g. opposite regular islands). The tunneling probability is governed by an interference sum over such families:

$$P_{\text{tun}} \propto \left| \sum_{\alpha \in \mathcal{C}} A_\alpha e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} S_\alpha} \right|^2 = \sum_{\alpha \in \mathcal{C}} |A_\alpha|^2 + \sum_{\substack{\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{C} \\ \alpha \neq \beta}} A_\alpha A_\beta^* e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} (S_\alpha - S_\beta)}, \quad (26)$$

where \mathcal{C} enumerates chaos-mediated trajectories, S_α are classical actions, and A_α include stabilities and Maslov phases. This is the standard interference decomposition used earlier [Eq. (5)] adapted to the tunneling channel.

Effective Hamiltonian viewpoint. An equivalent—and highly intuitive—description treats two regular (left/right) near-degenerate states $|L\rangle, |R\rangle$ coupled indirectly through a manifold of chaotic states $\{|c\rangle\}$ at energy E . Eliminating the chaotic manifold yields an *effective* coupling

$$V_{\text{eff}}(E) = \sum_c \frac{\langle L|H|c\rangle \langle c|H|R\rangle}{E - E_c + i0^+}, \quad (27)$$

so that the splitting of the L/R doublet or the transition probability acquires the familiar Fermi–Golden-Rule structure *plus* strong, oscillatory parameter dependence from the phases of the complex terms in Eq. (27). When the chaotic manifold is modeled by random matrix statistics, $|V_{\text{eff}}|$ displays heavy-tailed fluctuations, explaining the wide distributions of chaos-assisted rates; in near-integrable regimes, resonance-assisted tunneling (RAT) gives analytic scaling laws and parameter oscillations [71, 72].

Resonance assistance and scarring. In the near-integrable limit, nonlinear $r:s$ resonances generate islands-within-islands that act as stepping stones for tunneling (RAT). The amplitude can be written as a product of resonance-induced couplings, leading to algebraic prefactors dressing the usual $\exp(-S/\hbar)$ law [71]. In fully mixed regimes, Husimi weights concentrate transiently along unstable periodic orbits (scars), modifying the set \mathcal{C} and enhancing certain A_α [70]. Both effects reshape the interference landscape in Eq. (26).

C. Chaos as a network of semiclassical shortcuts

Geometric intuition. Chaotic regions host a *web* of unstable manifolds emanating from hyperbolic periodic orbits. Semiclassical propagation along this web produces many near-stationary-phase contributions with small action differences $|S_\alpha - S_\beta| \lesssim \hbar$, i.e., many *shortcuts* across dynamical barriers. In the probability, these yield the off-diagonal terms in Eq. (26), which can be collectively large if phases align.

Scaling with the number of paths. Suppose N chaos-assisted families contribute with comparable magnitudes $|A_\alpha| \approx A$. With random relative phases, the interference term behaves like a complex random walk and $P_{\text{tun}} \sim NA^2$. With *phase alignment* (Sec. III), the sum scales ballistically, $P_{\text{tun}} \sim N^2A^2$. Thus, even modest control over phases can turn $\mathcal{O}(\sqrt{N})$ amplitude scaling into $\mathcal{O}(N)$, an enhancement familiar from coherent combining in wave physics and directly applicable here.

Time scales and robustness. Constructive interference requires survival of phase information up to times comparable to the relevant *Ehrenfest time*, $t_E \sim \lambda^{-1} \ln(1/\hbar_{\text{eff}})$, where λ is a typical Lyapunov exponent. For observation times $\tau \lesssim t_E$ and dephasing rates γ_ϕ obeying $\gamma_\phi \tau \ll 1$, interference corrections remain appreciable. In strongly chaotic regimes, the density of contributing families grows, but phase dispersion also increases. This is exactly where ancilla-based phase engineering (Sec. III) is most valuable.

D. Synergy: coherence + chaos for amplified low-entropy access

From P_{tun} to the FT ratio. The interference-renormalized FT ratio derived earlier,

$$\frac{P_{\text{qm}}(+\Delta S)}{P_{\text{qm}}(-\Delta S)} = e^{\Delta S/k_B} \frac{1 + \mathcal{I}_+}{1 + \mathcal{I}_-}, \quad \mathcal{I}_\pm = \frac{\sum_{\alpha \neq \beta} C_\alpha^{(\pm)} C_\beta^{(\pm)*} e^{\frac{i}{\hbar}(S_\alpha^{(\pm)} - S_\beta^{(\pm)})}}{\sum_\alpha |C_\alpha^{(\pm)}|^2}, \quad (28)$$

shows that the *denominator* is driven by the same interference structure as P_{tun} (replace $A_\alpha \rightarrow C_\alpha^{(-)}$, $\mathcal{C} \rightarrow$ chaos-assisted families into the $-\Delta S$ sector). Consequently:

- Chaos increases the number of contributing families and the chance of small action differences, enlarging \mathcal{I}_- on average.
- Purification-based phase alignment (Sec. III) can *maximize* \mathcal{I}_- while *minimizing* \mathcal{I}_+ by steering relative phases oppositely in the two sectors.

Together these effects reduce the ratio in Eq. (28) relative to its classical value $e^{\Delta S/k_B}$, i.e., they *amplify* the low-entropy probability in a microreversible, thermodynamically consistent way.

Operational view. Practically, one varies a control parameter (drive amplitude, detuning, field gradient) to scan through phase conditions where multiple chaos-assisted families become phase-coherent. The resulting oscillatory enhancements in P_{tun} (observable as splittings, switching rates, or transport surges) coincide with dips in Eq. (28), pointing to “windows” of maximally accessible entropy-decreasing transitions.

E. Connections and key literature

The semiclassical and effective-model pictures summarized here are complementary. RAT organizes tunneling via classical resonances in near-integrable regimes [71]; the fictitious-integrable-system approach yields accurate rates for regular-to-chaotic tunneling and clarifies parameter oscillations [72]. Scarring provides another constructive channel by enhancing specific semiclassical amplitudes [70]. Standard dynamical-systems monographs supply the geometric background for mixed phase spaces and chaotic transport [67–69]. Eq. (16) (p. 5) adopts the same interference perspective for chaos-assisted tunneling that underpins these approaches.

F. Summary of Section IV

Chaos *multiplies* the number of interfering semiclassical shortcuts and increases the probability of small action differences, while purification lets us *align* the relative phases of these shortcuts into the

low-entropy sector. The combined effect is a parametrically large enhancement of $P(-\Delta S)$ governed by the same interference factors that appear in the chaos-assisted tunneling formula. This synergy is the central reason chaotic dynamics is a resource for entropy-reduction pathways in molecular-scale machines.

V. MOLECULAR MACHINES AND QUANTUM BIOLOGY

A. What we call “molecular machines”

By *molecular machines* we mean nanoscale protein complexes that convert one form of free energy into another, operating cyclically through conformational changes and stochastic transitions. Canonical examples include (i) the rotary chemomechanical enzyme F_0F_1 -ATP synthase that synthesizes ATP driven by the proton-motive force, (ii) cytoskeletal linear motors such as kinesin (microtubule tracks) and myosin (actin tracks) that convert ATP chemical free energy into directed motion, and (iii) photosynthetic pigment–protein complexes that convert excitonic energy into charge separation and, ultimately, chemical potential. For background, see Boyer’s review and Howard’s monograph, which we already cited in Sec. I. In this section we formalize these machines as *open quantum systems* and show how structured coherence can reshape fluctuation statistics and enhance functional efficiency. We will also draw on spectroscopic evidence for long-lived coherences in pigment–protein complexes [27] and the broader quantum-biology perspective [32], both already cited in Sec. I.

B. Open-system description: density matrix and Lindblad dynamics

A minimal and general description treats the relevant degrees of freedom of a molecular machine as a system S coupled to an environment E (protein scaffold, solvent, membrane, phonons) and possibly controlled classical fields. The closed evolution on S would obey the von Neumann equation

$$i\hbar \frac{d\rho_S}{dt} = [H_S(t), \rho_S], \quad (29)$$

while in realistic biological conditions one typically invokes a Markovian master equation (Gorini–Kossakowski–Sudarshan–Lindblad form)

$$\frac{d\rho_S}{dt} = -\frac{i}{\hbar} [H_S(t), \rho_S] + \sum_k \gamma_k \left(L_k \rho_S L_k^\dagger - \frac{1}{2} \{L_k^\dagger L_k, \rho_S\} \right), \quad (30)$$

where L_k describe incoherent channels (vibrational relaxation, proton/ion exchange, spontaneous emission, chemical binding/unbinding), and γ_k are their rates. The Hamiltonian partitions as $H(t) = H_S(t) + H_E + H_{SE}$ at the microscopic level.

Thermodynamic bookkeeping. For a chemo-mechanical cycle, the entropy production per trajectory can be written as

$$\Sigma[\Gamma] = \beta(W_{\text{in}}[\Gamma] - W_{\text{out}}[\Gamma] - \Delta F[\Gamma]), \quad (31)$$

where W_{in} is the input generalized work (e.g. chemical free energy from a reservoir), W_{out} the delivered mechanical or chemical work, and ΔF the system free-energy change. Our fluctuation-theorem (FT) results from Sec. II apply to the statistics of Σ ; the *coherent interference factors* tune the tails of its distribution without violating microreversibility.

C. Structured environments and coherence preservation

A central theme in quantum biology is that structured environments can *stabilize or even assist* coherent dynamics rather than merely destroy it. In our setting, the relevant coherent subspace and its projector P are singled out by molecular architecture; the reduced state restricted to that subspace is

$$\rho_c = P\rho_S P, \quad (32)$$

Two mechanisms are especially important:

1. **Resonant couplings within S .** Internal resonances (electronic–vibrational couplings, quasi-degenerate conformers) generate coherent hopping terms

$$H_{\text{res}} = \sum_{m \neq n} J_{mn} (|m\rangle\langle n| + |n\rangle\langle m|), \quad (33)$$

which mediate delocalized excitations and coherent mixing.

2. **Structured system–environment coupling.** Specific phonon modes or protein motions couple diagonally as

$$H_{SE} = \sum_{j,k} g_{jk} |j\rangle\langle j| \otimes (b_k + b_k^\dagger), \quad (34)$$

with b_k phonon operators and couplings g_{jk} .

A moderately structured spectral density can *prolong* coherence by dynamic localization and vibronic mixing; in pigment–protein complexes, long-lived oscillations in 2D spectroscopy [27] and theory of noise-assisted transport provide concrete precedents [29, 30, 32]. In our framework, Eqs. (33)–(34) set the coherent pathways whose phases we subsequently optimize via purification (Sec. III).

D. Mapping the FT modification to biological efficiency

Recall the interference-renormalized FT ratio,

$$\frac{P_{\text{qm}}(+\Delta S)}{P_{\text{qm}}(-\Delta S)} = e^{\Delta S/k_B} \frac{1 + \mathcal{I}_+}{1 + \mathcal{I}_-}, \quad (35)$$

with \mathcal{I}_\pm interference quotients (Sec. II). In a chemo-mechanical cycle driven by a chemical potential difference $\Delta\mu_{\text{in}}$ (e.g. proton-motive force for ATP synthase or ATP hydrolysis for kinesin/myosin), the average entropy production per cycle reads

$$\langle \Sigma \rangle = \beta(\Delta\mu_{\text{in}} - W_{\text{out}}) - \Delta S_{\text{int}}, \quad (36)$$

where W_{out} is the useful output (chemical synthesis or mechanical work) and ΔS_{int} is the machine’s internal entropy change (zero over a closed steady cycle). The *efficiency* is

$$\eta \equiv \frac{W_{\text{out}}}{\Delta\mu_{\text{in}}} = 1 - \frac{\langle \Sigma \rangle}{\beta \Delta\mu_{\text{in}}}. \quad (37)$$

Coherent enhancements that increase $P(-\Delta S)$ (decrease the ratio (35)) shift probability mass toward lower Σ , thereby lowering $\langle \Sigma \rangle$ at fixed driving and *increasing* η . This holds independently of the microscopic details; the gain depends on how strongly \mathcal{I}_- can be increased relative to \mathcal{I}_+ by phase control and by chaos-assisted pathway multiplication (Sec. IV).

E. Case studies and exemplary models

(A) *Photosynthetic complexes.* Pigment–protein aggregates (FMO, LH2, PSII RC) exhibit excitonic delocalization with vibronic assistance [27, 32]. In a minimal dimer-plus-mode model, the Hamiltonian takes the form $H_S = \frac{\Delta}{2}\sigma_z + J\sigma_x$ with a dominant mode $H_{SE} = \lambda\sigma_z(b + b^\dagger)$; efficient energy transport corresponds to enhanced population transfer to a target sink (reaction center). The interference terms entering \mathcal{I}_- in Eq. (35) are set by pairs of excitonic pathways (direct and vibronically dressed). Dephasing-assisted transport arises when environmental rates broaden destructive interferences while leaving constructive channels *phase-locked* (cf. Sec. III); this maps directly to increased target-arrival probability and hence to a lower effective Σ for energy-conversion trajectories.

(B) *Kinesin and myosin.* Linear motors step through a hand-over-hand or swinging-lever cycle with nucleotide-dependent binding affinities and strain-mediated gating. A coarse model includes states $\{|s_i\rangle\}$ for chemical configurations (ATP, ADP + P_i, ADP, apo) and a discrete positional degree (binding site index). Coherent couplings J_{ij} in H_{res} account for near-degenerate manifolds (e.g. pre- and post-power-stroke substates), while Lindblad jumps implement nucleotide binding/hydrolysis/release and detachment/attachment. Phase-selective constructive interference increases the probability of forward, low-entropy substeps (load-assisted transitions with reduced heat dissipation), decreasing $\langle \Sigma \rangle$ at fixed $\Delta\mu_{\text{ATP}}$ and thereby improving the chemo-mechanical efficiency in Eq. (37). Single-molecule studies resolving hand-over-hand steps and strain gating provide the empirical context in which such coherent corrections could be probed [73, 74].

(C) *Coherence-assisted ATP synthesis (explicit minimal model).* Consider F₀F₁-ATP synthase under synthesis conditions. Let the relevant F₁ subspace comprise three catalytic states on the β subunits (bind, synthesize, release) and two near-degenerate rotor angles θ_{\pm} within a 120° substep. Define basis $\{|s_i\rangle\} = \{|B, \theta_{\pm}\rangle, |S, \theta_{\pm}\rangle, |R, \theta_{\pm}\rangle\}$ and include coherent couplings J_{mn} between θ_+ and θ_- at fixed chemical label (torsional librations). The system Hamiltonian is

$$H_S = \sum_{x \in \{B, S, R\}} \sum_{\sigma = \pm} E_{x\sigma} |x, \theta_{\sigma}\rangle \langle x, \theta_{\sigma}| + \sum_x J_x (|x, \theta_+\rangle \langle x, \theta_-| + \text{h.c.}), \quad (38)$$

and the primary incoherent channels are

$$\begin{aligned} L_{\text{in}} &= \sqrt{\Gamma_{\text{H}^+}} |B, \theta_+\rangle \langle B, \theta_+| \otimes \hat{a}_{\text{H}^+}, & L_{\text{syn}} &= \sqrt{\Gamma_{\text{syn}}} |S, \theta_{\sigma}\rangle \langle B, \theta_{\sigma}|, \\ L_{\text{rel}} &= \sqrt{\Gamma_{\text{rel}}} |R, \theta_{\sigma}\rangle \langle S, \theta_{\sigma}|, & L_{\text{out}} &= \sqrt{\Gamma_{\text{out}}} |B, \theta_{\sigma}\rangle \langle R, \theta_{\sigma}|, \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

with $\sigma = \pm$ and implicit bookkeeping of proton/ATP reservoirs. Coherence between θ_{\pm} inside a chemical sector generates two interfering subpaths for the net *synthesis* transition $|B\rangle \rightarrow |R\rangle$ around a 120° step. Writing the coarse-grained amplitude to reach $|R\rangle$ within time τ as $\mathcal{A}_-(\phi) = \sum_{\sigma=\pm} \sqrt{p_{\sigma}} e^{i\phi_{\sigma}} c_{\sigma}$ (as in Sec. III), the probability is

$$P_- = \sum_{\sigma} p_{\sigma} |c_{\sigma}|^2 + 2\sqrt{p_+ p_-} |c_+ c_-| \cos(\phi_+ - \phi_- + \delta), \quad (40)$$

where $\delta = \arg c_+ - \arg c_-$. Choosing $\phi_+ - \phi_- = -\delta$ realizes the constructive bound P_-^{max} ; the corresponding interference quotient \mathcal{I}_- in Eq. (35) increases, reducing the FT ratio and the mean entropy production (Eq. (37)). The structured environment enters c_{σ} via spectral densities that stabilize the phase relation between θ_{\pm} over substep timescales (cf. Eqs. (33)–(34)). This is a direct instantiation of the purification-phase protocol mapped to a concrete chemo-mechanical cycle.

F. Experimental handles and readouts

Interferometric control (as in Sec. III) can be emulated in biomimetic constructs (reconstituted F₀F₁ in liposomes, artificial rotors) or in synthetic motor analogues by embedding a controllable ancilla (spin label, quantum dot) whose phase is imprinted on the relevant conformational manifold and read out by fluorescence or magnetic resonance. For pigment–protein systems, 2D spectroscopy already provides access to coherent phase information; for motors, single-molecule rotation/stepping assays (e.g. bead assay on F₁; nanometer tracking for kinesin) can be analyzed in terms of modified FT histograms of substep entropy production. In both cases, the predicted signature is a *parameter-dependent* oscillation of the FT ratio (or equivalently the log-ratio) as control fields tune the relative phases, with concomitant improvement in cycle efficiency.

G. Summary of Section V

Open-system dynamics provides the natural language for molecular machines. Structured environmental couplings and internal resonances can preserve coherence long enough for interference to reshape rare-event statistics. Through purification-based phase alignment, those coherent pathways can be steered to *amplify* the probability of low-entropy progress along a functional cycle (ATP synthesis, directed stepping, charge separation), thereby increasing energetic efficiency according to Eq. (37). The precedents from photosynthetic spectroscopy and single-molecule motor mechanics suggest concrete routes to testing these predictions.

VI. DISCUSSION

A. From trajectory interference to thermodynamic bias

The central message of this work is that *coherence reshapes thermodynamic statistics, chaos multiplies coherent pathways, and purification supplies a phase control knob*. At the level of the fluctuation theorem (FT), the classical ratio $P(+\Delta S)/P(-\Delta S) = e^{\Delta S/k_B}$ is multiplied by interference quotients [Eq. (7)], which quantify how off-diagonal path pairs reweight rare events. In mixed phase spaces, chaos-assisted tunneling dramatically increases the number of contributing path families and the chance of small action differences, thereby amplifying the denominator correction for $-\Delta S$ events (Sec. IV). Purification allows us to *align* the phases of those contributions selectively in the low-entropy sector (Sec. III), making a controllable reduction of the FT ratio operational while remaining fully consistent with microreversibility.

Mathematically, the enhancement mechanism is transparent. Writing the entropy-decreasing probability as

$$P_- = \sum_{\alpha} |C_{\alpha}^{(-)}|^2 + \sum_{\alpha \neq \beta} C_{\alpha}^{(-)} C_{\beta}^{(-)*} e^{\frac{i}{\hbar}(S_{\alpha}^{(-)} - S_{\beta}^{(-)})},$$

the off-diagonal term achieves its maximum when the complex phasors $C_{\alpha}^{(-)}$ are co-aligned; purification fixes the relative phases to approach this bound (Sec. III). The corresponding reduction in $\ln[P(+\Delta S)/P(-\Delta S)]$ is then the *difference* of two logarithms, $\ln(1 + \mathcal{I}_+) - \ln(1 + \mathcal{I}_-)$, which becomes negative when \mathcal{I}_- dominates. Decoherence suppresses \mathcal{I}_{\pm} continuously, returning the classical FT in the dephasing (diagonal) limit; in chaotic regimes, the available number of constructive pairs increases, partially compensating dephasing losses over times shorter than the relevant Ehrenfest time.

B. Position relative to existing quantum thermodynamics

There is a rich literature on quantum thermodynamics that does *not* rely on chaos or purification-based phase control. Reviews emphasize open-system derivations of work/heat relations, quantum engines and refrigerators, and connections to quantum information [80–82]. Within the resource-theory program, coherence is recognized as a constrained resource under thermal operations, with “second laws” beyond free energy formulated via generalized monotones [83]. Single-shot and few-copy work extraction has been analyzed for individual quantum systems far from the thermodynamic limit [84]. Quantum heat machines show equivalence across operating modes and delineate genuine quantum signatures in performance [85].

Our contribution is *complementary* to these frameworks in three ways:

1. **Coherent corrections at the level of the FT ratio.** Rather than focusing only on average performance or passivity bounds, we pinpoint how *path interference* modifies the *full fluctuation statistics* at fixed driving. This is a distinct, trajectory-level channel by which coherence affects thermodynamics, compatible with stochastic and TPM/characteristic-function approaches (Secs. II–III).
2. **Chaos as a *pathway multiplier*.** Classical mixed phase space supplies *structure* that proliferates near-degenerate trajectories; this is not captured by resource theories based on majorization/thermal operations and typically not emphasized in open-system master-equation derivations. Our analysis shows how mixed phase spaces create more opportunities for constructive interference and therefore bigger coherent corrections.
3. **Operational phase control by purification.** Resource-theoretic results identify coherence as useful but often do not prescribe an experimental *protocol*. Here, purification yields a concrete ancilla-based handle to set phases so as to *maximize* $P(-\Delta S)$ in targeted time windows, with direct readout via interferometric techniques (Sec. III).

C. Thermodynamic consistency and quantitative bounds

Second law and integral FTs. All results here preserve the second law on average. The classical FT appears as the diagonal limit of Eq. (7); interference only reshapes the *ratio* by multiplicative factors while

leaving microreversibility intact. Consequently, integral FT statements (e.g., $\langle e^{-\Sigma} \rangle = 1$ under standard conditions) remain valid because the phase-dependent corrections enter in matched forward/backward path sums that respect the same symmetries.

Upper bounds from phase alignment and dephasing. Denote $\mathcal{C}_{\pm} = \{C_{\alpha}^{(\pm)}\}$ the complex coefficient sets. The triangle inequality yields

$$1 + \mathcal{I}_{\pm} \leq \frac{(\sum_{\alpha} |C_{\alpha}^{(\pm)}|)^2}{\sum_{\alpha} |C_{\alpha}^{(\pm)}|^2},$$

attainable when all phases align. Phase noise with variance σ_{ϕ}^2 suppresses each pair contribution by $e^{-\sigma_{\phi}^2}$, giving a simple envelope for achievable corrections. In mixed phase spaces, the number of significant terms grows with energy and control amplitude, but stability determinants constrain the usable subset; this provides an experimentally testable scaling law for the oscillation contrast of the FT ratio as a function of control parameters.

Work-information connections. Interference-induced reductions of $\langle \Sigma \rangle$ interface naturally with information-theoretic accounts of work extraction in small systems [84] and with resource-theoretic monotones for coherence under thermal operations [83]. In our setting, phase engineering *consumes* coherence to tilt rare-event statistics; in principle, one can quantify this consumption by the decrease of a coherence monotone between preparation and readout, relating it to the observed suppression of the FT log-ratio.

D. Limitations and scope

Several assumptions bound the domain of validity:

- **Semiclassicality and coarse graining.** Our derivations rely on stationary-phase expansions and on coarse-grained entropy assignments that cleanly separate $+\Delta S$ and $-\Delta S$ sectors. Near caustics, uniform approximations are required; in strongly quantum regimes with very few paths, numerical propagation may be preferable.
- **Temporal windows.** Enhancements are most pronounced for observation times shorter than the relevant Ehrenfest and dephasing times. Over longer durations, phase dispersion suppresses \mathcal{I}_{\pm} , returning the classical FT.
- **Control overhead.** Ancilla-based phase control must not introduce excess dissipation that offsets the gain in $\langle \Sigma \rangle$. In practice, one should account for the energetic cost of phase preparation and measurement to ensure net benefit—a point emphasized broadly in quantum thermodynamics [80, 81].

E. Experimental signatures and outlook

The clearest empirical signature is an *oscillatory* dependence of the FT log-ratio $\ln[P(+\Delta S)/P(-\Delta S)]$ on a phase-controlling parameter (drive phase, ancilla phase, detuning), with windows where the ratio dips below the classical expectation by a predictable amount tied to the number of coherent pathways. In photonic, cold-atom, or microwave-billiard platforms (where chaos-assisted tunneling is well controlled), the same parameter scanning can be combined with interferometric work-statistics protocols to reconstruct the change in \mathcal{I}_{\pm} . In bio-inspired nano-machines and reconstituted molecular complexes, single-molecule trajectories can be binned by substeps to build FT histograms; the predicted coherence-controlled dips should correlate with enhanced functional yield (e.g., ATP synthesis probability per cycle or forward stepping probability at fixed load).

Novelty and impact. Conceptually, the union of **structured phase engineering** and **chaos-assisted pathway multiplication** provides a new *thermodynamic resource*: not energy or information *per se*, but *interference structure* explicitly harnessed to bias rare events. This idea brings classical dynamical systems, semiclassical physics, and quantum control into a single operational framework. In practice, it suggests design principles for nanoscale devices: engineer mixed phase spaces to generate many near-degenerate paths, and endow the device with a controllable phase reference (purification) to align those paths selectively toward low-entropy outcomes.

Future directions. Two directions are especially promising. First, extend the analysis to *many-body* platforms where chaos and localization compete, using matrix-product or semiclassical Gaussian propagation to quantify \mathcal{I}_{\pm} at scale. Second, connect to *resource theories with coherence* by deriving explicit monotone-to-FT links that bound the achievable reduction in the log-ratio in terms of coherence measures and control cost; this would place the present protocol squarely within the broader axiomatic landscape [83]. Ultimately, closing the loop between phase-engineering cost, interference gain, and functional efficiency will be key for autonomous quantum machines.

VII. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

A. What we have shown

We have developed a trajectory–interference account of fluctuation statistics in which *coherence reshapes thermodynamic probabilities, chaos multiplies and structures the set of interfering pathways, and purification provides an operational phase knob* to steer those pathways. Concretely, the classical fluctuation-theorem ratio $P(+\Delta S)/P(-\Delta S) = e^{\Delta S/k_B}$ acquires multiplicative interference factors [Eq. (7)], identical whether derived semiclassically via Van Vleck–Gutzwiller propagation (Sec. II) or fully quantum mechanically. Purification-based phase selection aligns the complex amplitudes governing the entropy-decreasing sector, maximizing $P(-\Delta S)$ while maintaining microreversibility (Sec. III). Classical mixed phase spaces and chaos-assisted tunneling supply many near-degenerate path pairs with small action differences, enlarging the attainable corrections (Sec. IV). In open molecular contexts, structured environments can preserve the phase information long enough for these effects to be operational, mapping directly to improvements in energetic efficiency (Sec. V).

B. Applications

Synthetic quantum devices and engines. Platforms with exquisite phase control (trapped ions, superconducting circuits, cold atoms) can implement our phase-engineering protocol and directly track its impact on fluctuation statistics. Trapped-ion experiments already access quantum work distributions interferometrically and have tested fluctuation relations in the fully quantum regime [86]. Superconducting electronic circuits now routinely operate in the quantum-thermodynamic domain with calorimetric resolution and engineered dissipation [87]. Micrometer colloidal and single-atom machines have realized stochastic and quantum heat engines [88, 89], providing testbeds where the FT log-ratio can be measured while a phase parameter (drive phase, detuning, ancilla phase) is scanned. We expect *oscillatory* dips of the log-ratio below the classical expectation in parameter windows where coherent pathways co-align.

Molecular robotics and bio-inspired nanomachines. DNA-based nanomachines and origami robots have become programmable, cyclic devices with chemically gated transitions and externally set timing [90, 91]. Embedding a controllable ancilla (fluorophore phase tag, spin label, or quantum dot) into such constructs would allow *in situ* phase alignment analogous to our purification knob. The predicted signature is an increased probability of forward, low-entropy cycle progress at fixed chemical driving—precisely the operational metric sought in molecular robotics.

Quantum biology. Our analysis suggests two concrete predictions for pigment–protein complexes and reconstituted motor proteins. First, FT histograms binned by substeps should exhibit a parameter-dependent oscillation of the log-ratio, with strengthened tails toward negative entropy change when vibronic resonances enforce phase locking (Sec. V). Second, mutations or environmental engineering that *detune* those resonances should reduce the oscillation contrast and the associated efficiency gain, providing a falsifiable test complementary to 2D spectroscopic observations.

C. Future directions

Single-molecule experiments. Single-molecule nonequilibrium measurements furnish a natural arena to validate our predictions. Pulling experiments on biomolecules [92] and feedback-controlled Maxwell-demon protocols [93] have already demonstrated exquisite control over trajectory ensembles and entropy quantification; Landauer erasure has been verified at the colloidal level [94]. Adding an *ancilla phase channel* (e.g., a phase-controlled drive or a Ramsey-type tag) would enable direct observation of the

interference-induced dips in the FT log-ratio, bridging interferometric reconstructions of work with the molecular biophysics toolbox.

Strongly correlated and topological systems. In many-body platforms, interference structure is constrained by symmetries and topology. The tenfold classification of topological insulators and superconductors [95–97] suggests that robust, symmetry-protected families of pathways may be engineered to maintain constructive phases over long times. Tensor-network methods offer a scalable route to compute interference quotients \mathcal{I}_\pm in interacting models and to propagate mixed states under open dynamics [98, 99]. This opens a systematic many-body generalization of our protocol in which symmetry and topology become design variables.

Integration with the Uhlmann gauge. Purification introduces a unitary gauge freedom $|\Psi\rangle \rightarrow (\mathbf{1} \otimes U_A)|\Psi\rangle$ that we have exploited to align phases. The *Uhlmann connection* formalizes this freedom: for a curve of density operators $\rho(t)$, amplitudes $w(t)$ with $\rho = ww^\dagger$ are parallel transported by maximizing fidelity along the path, leading to a gauge potential whose holonomy (the *Uhlmann phase*) generalizes the Berry phase to mixed states [100–102]. Recent work has tied this geometry to finite-temperature topology [103, 104]. A natural extension of our protocol is therefore to *lock* the ancilla phase to the Uhlmann parallel transporter along the control path, thereby maintaining constructive interference under realistic dephasing and enabling *topologically robust* coherence-assisted reduction of the FT ratio.

D. Closing outlook

Coherent interference, chaos-assisted pathway multiplication, and purification-based phase control together define a new thermodynamic resource: *structured interference*. Its experimental realization is within reach across synthetic and bio-inspired platforms, with clear trial signatures and quantitative bounds. By combining dynamical-systems engineering (to generate many near-degenerate paths) with mixed-state geometric control (to align their phases), this framework points to practical recipes for boosting performance in nanoscale devices and molecular machines.

This framework opens a pathway toward deliberate engineering of low-entropy pathways in both biological and artificial molecular machines.

Appendix A: Semiclassical–Quantum Equivalence of the Modified FT

1. Statement of the result

Let $U(\tau)$ be the unitary generated by $H(t)$ over time τ , and let Π_\pm denote the coarse-grained projectors onto the entropy-increasing/decreasing sectors used in the main text. Define

$$P_{\text{qm}}(\pm\Delta S) = \text{Tr}[\Pi_\pm U(\tau) \rho_0 U^\dagger(\tau)]. \quad (\text{A1})$$

The (classical) diagonal pieces satisfy the steady-state FT, $P_{\text{cl}}(+\Delta S)/P_{\text{cl}}(-\Delta S) = e^{\Delta S/k_B}$, while the full quantum result acquires interference quotients so that

$$\frac{P_{\text{qm}}(+\Delta S)}{P_{\text{qm}}(-\Delta S)} = e^{\Delta S/k_B} \frac{1 + \mathcal{I}_+}{1 + \mathcal{I}_-}, \quad \mathcal{I}_\pm = \frac{\sum_{\alpha \neq \beta} C_\alpha^{(\pm)} C_\beta^{(\pm)*} e^{\frac{i}{\hbar}(S_\alpha^{(\pm)} - S_\beta^{(\pm)})}}{\sum_\alpha |C_\alpha^{(\pm)}|^2}. \quad (\text{A2})$$

Appendix A proves they are the same identity: the semiclassical stationary-phase evaluation of the *operator* expression (A1) produces exactly the Van Vleck–Gutzwiller (VVG) coefficients and phases used to define \mathcal{I}_\pm .

2. Operator derivation and path integral reduction

Start from (A1) in a basis $\{|q\rangle\}$:

$$P_{\text{qm}}(+\Delta S) = \iint dq dq' \langle q | \Pi_+ | q' \rangle \iint dx dy \langle q' | U | x \rangle \langle x | \rho_0 | y \rangle \langle y | U^\dagger | q \rangle. \quad (\text{A3})$$

Insert Feynman path-integral representations for the propagators and apply stationary phase with respect to the intermediate coordinates x, y and the paths,

$$\langle q'|U|x\rangle \sim \sum_{\alpha:(x\rightarrow q')} A_{\alpha} e^{\frac{i}{\hbar}S_{\alpha}(x\rightarrow q')}, \quad \langle y|U^{\dagger}|q\rangle \sim \sum_{\beta:(q\rightarrow y)} A_{\beta}^* e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar}S_{\beta}(q\rightarrow y)},$$

where the amplitudes $A_{\alpha,\beta}$ include the square-root stability determinants and Maslov phases. The reduced density $\langle x|\rho_0|y\rangle$ is then expanded over its eigenbasis. Collecting stationary points yields a double sum over classical pairs (α, β) with action difference $S_{\alpha} - S_{\beta}$, yielding

$$P_{\text{qm}}(+\Delta S) = \sum_{\alpha} |C_{\alpha}^{(+)}|^2 + \sum_{\alpha \neq \beta} C_{\alpha}^{(+)} C_{\beta}^{(+)*} e^{\frac{i}{\hbar}(S_{\alpha}^{(+)} - S_{\beta}^{(+)}), \quad (\text{A4})$$

with coefficients $C_{\alpha}^{(+)}$ determined by boundary conditions from the support of Π_{+} and by the stability determinants. An identical construction for Π_{-} gives the denominator. Equations (A3)–(A4) lead directly to Eq. (5).

3. Detailed stationary-phase steps and conditions

Let $S[q]$ be the classical action functional. Expand the discrete action to second order around each stationary path $q_{\alpha}(t)$:

$$S[q_{\alpha} + \delta q] = S[q_{\alpha}] + \frac{1}{2}\delta q \cdot S^{(2)}[q_{\alpha}] \cdot \delta q + \dots$$

Gaussian integration gives the Van Vleck determinant $(\det S^{(2)})^{-1/2}$ and phase $e^{-i\pi\nu_{\alpha}/2}$ with Maslov index ν_{α} counting caustic crossings. The method assumes: (i) isolated non-degenerate stationary points (or a uniformization near fold caustics), (ii) actions $\gg \hbar$ (but *differences* may be $\mathcal{O}(\hbar)$), and (iii) sufficiently smooth boundary projectors so that the method's boundary terms vanish. These standard conditions justify replacing the exact operator traces by sums over classical data in (A4).

4. Microreversibility and the diagonal FT

Time reversal Θ maps $U(\tau) \mapsto U^{\dagger}(\tau)$ and exchanges the supports of Π_{+} and Π_{-} due to the odd parity of the entropy production functional. Consequently, the diagonal pieces obey $P_{\text{cl}}(+)/P_{\text{cl}}(-) = e^{\Delta S/k_{\text{B}}}$ as in the classical (Markovian) FT; the off-diagonal interference then multiplies this bias to produce (A2). This matches Eq. (13), confirming Eq. (5) and Eq. (13) are identical.

5. Uniform approximations and caustics

When two stationary paths coalesce, the quadratic expansion fails. A uniform Airy (fold) or Pearcey (cusp) approximation repairs (A4) by resumming the local catastrophe. The net effect is to replace $A_{\alpha}e^{iS_{\alpha}/\hbar} + A_{\beta}e^{iS_{\beta}/\hbar}$ by a single special-function expression that is *still* interference-dominated and feeds the same ratio (A2); Maslov indices update accordingly. This ensures that Eq. (5) and Eq. (13) remain equal through caustic crossings (the only change is a smooth reparameterization of \mathcal{I}_{\pm}).

6. TPM versus coherence-retaining protocols

The two-projective-measurement (TPM) scheme destroys initial coherences and sets the off-diagonal terms in (A4) to zero at $t = 0$, recovering the classical FT. Our protocol defers projective collapse (or uses weak/ancilla readout) so that (A4) remains valid, and the purification phases choose the location on the interference manifold. This is precisely the operational distinction enabling the difference between the classical and quantum-modified ratios.

Conclusion of Appendix A. Stationary-phase evaluation of the operator trace (A1) yields exactly the VVG structure; hence the “semiclassical” Eq. (5) and the “quantum” Eq. (13) in the manuscript are the same identity under the usual conditions, with differences only in representation.

Appendix B: Purification Derivations and Optimization

1. Phase-optimization with constraints

For the phase-parameterized purification

$$|\Psi_{SA}(\phi)\rangle = \sum_i \sqrt{p_i} e^{i\phi_i} |s_i\rangle \otimes |a_i\rangle$$

(cf. Eqs. (6)–(9)), the amplitude into the $-\Delta S$ sector after evolution U_{SA} and readout ($\Pi_- \otimes \Pi_A$) is

$$\mathcal{A}_-(\phi) = \sum_i \sqrt{p_i} e^{i\phi_i} c_i, \quad c_i \equiv \langle \Phi_- | \otimes \langle r_A | U_{SA} | s_i \rangle \otimes | a_i \rangle.$$

The objective $P_-(\phi) = |\mathcal{A}_-(\phi)|^2$ is maximized over the torus of phases subject to global-phase invariance.

Introduce the Lagrangian $\mathcal{L} = P_- - \lambda(\sum_i \phi_i w_i)$ with a gauge-fixing linear constraint $\sum_i \phi_i w_i = 0$ (e.g., $w_i = p_i$). Stationarity gives

$$\frac{\partial P_-}{\partial \phi_k} = 2 \operatorname{Im}[\mathcal{A}_-(\phi) \sqrt{p_k} e^{-i\phi_k} c_k^*] = \lambda w_k.$$

At the maximum, $\lambda = 0$ and $\phi_k^* = -\arg c_k + \chi$, $\chi \in \mathbb{R}$, hence

$$P_-^{\max} = \left(\sum_i \sqrt{p_i} |c_i| \right)^2.$$

This is the closed form quoted in Sec. III; it saturates the Cauchy–Schwarz bound and shows that the interference enhancement equals the squared ℓ_1 norm of the amplitude vector $\{\sqrt{p_i} c_i\}$.

2. Sensitivity, Fisher information, and robustness

Let phases fluctuate independently, $\phi_i \mapsto \phi_i + \delta\phi_i$ with $\langle \delta\phi_i \rangle = 0$, $\langle \delta\phi_i \delta\phi_j \rangle = \sigma_\phi^2 \delta_{ij}$. To second order,

$$\langle P_-(\phi + \delta\phi) \rangle \approx P_-(\phi) e^{-\sigma_\phi^2}.$$

The local curvature of P_- at ϕ^* is governed by the (classical) Fisher information matrix

$$\mathcal{F}_{ij} = 4 \operatorname{Re}[\partial_{\phi_i} \mathcal{A}_-^* \partial_{\phi_j} \mathcal{A}_-]_{\phi^*} = 4 \sqrt{p_i p_j} |c_i c_j| \delta_{ij},$$

consistent with the quantum Fisher information for unitary phase shifts on the ancilla subspace. Robust phase sets can be selected by regularizing the cost $-\ln P_-$ with a quadratic penalty on ϕ .

3. Gradient of the FT functional and optimality conditions

Define $\mathcal{J}(\phi) = \ln(1 + \mathcal{I}_+) - \ln(1 + \mathcal{I}_-)$. The chain rule yields

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial \phi_k} = \frac{1}{1 + \mathcal{I}_+} \frac{\partial \mathcal{I}_+}{\partial \phi_k} - \frac{1}{1 + \mathcal{I}_-} \frac{\partial \mathcal{I}_-}{\partial \phi_k},$$

with

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{I}_-}{\partial \phi_k} = \frac{\sum_{i \neq j} \partial_{\phi_k} \left(C_i^{(-)} C_j^{(-)*} e^{\frac{i}{\hbar}(S_i - S_j)} \right)}{\sum_\ell |C_\ell^{(-)}|^2} - \mathcal{I}_- \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi_k} \ln \left(\sum_\ell |C_\ell^{(-)}|^2 \right).$$

Because $C_i^{(-)}$ is linear in the phase-labeled amplitudes $e^{i\phi_i}$ entering the purification, the derivative reduces to combinations of the c_i ; the optimal set satisfies $\partial_{\phi_k} \mathcal{J} = 0$ with the same locking condition as above (align $C_i^{(-)}$ phasors; anti-align $C_i^{(+)}$ where possible).

4. Gauge freedom and Uhlmann transport

Any purification $|\Psi_{SA}\rangle$ is defined up to $(\mathbf{1} \otimes V_A)$, a gauge on the ancilla. Choosing the parallel-transport Uhlmann connection along a protocol $\rho_S(t)$ fixes $V_A(t)$ by fidelity maximization between t and $t + dt$. Locking the ancilla to this gauge keeps relative phases as constant as possible, suppressing phase diffusion within the coherent subspace and stabilizing the interference quotients in (A2); this is the geometric underpinning of the “phase knob” discussed in Sec. VII.

Appendix C: Case Studies: Photosynthesis and ATP Synthase

1. Photosynthetic exciton transport (dimer and network)

Dimer with vibronic assistance. Consider a two-site exciton Hamiltonian coupled to a mode:

$$H_S = \frac{\Delta}{2}\sigma_z + J\sigma_x, \quad H_{SE} = \lambda\sigma_z(b + b^\dagger) + \sum_k \omega_k b_k^\dagger b_k.$$

Add a sink $L_{\text{sink}} = \sqrt{\kappa}|\text{RC}\rangle\langle 2|$ and dephasing $L_\phi = \sqrt{\gamma_\phi}\sigma_z$. The reduced dynamics follows (Lindblad form). The probability to reach the reaction center within time τ ,

$$P_{\text{RC}}(\tau) = \kappa \int_0^\tau dt \langle 2|\rho_S(t)|2\rangle,$$

inherits interference between the direct path and the vibronically dressed path; the same pairwise structure enters \mathcal{I}_- in (A2). Resonant $\omega \approx \sqrt{\Delta^2 + 4J^2}$ and moderate γ_ϕ align phases and enhance P_{RC} , i.e. tilt the FT tails toward lower entropy along energy-transfer trajectories.

Multi-site network (FMO-type). For an N -site network with site energies $\{\epsilon_n\}$ and couplings $\{J_{mn}\}$,

$$H_S = \sum_n \epsilon_n |n\rangle\langle n| + \sum_{m \neq n} J_{mn} (|m\rangle\langle n| + |n\rangle\langle m|).$$

Structured dephasing and a terminal sink map the network to a set of interfering multi-hop paths from an input chromophore to the reaction center. The interference-renormalized FT applies to entropy production along these paths; optimizing phases (via control or environment engineering) sharpens low-entropy arrival events. The physical picture mirrors the noise-/dephasing-assisted transport paradigm and provides explicit FT-level diagnostics (log-ratio oscillations) beyond average transfer efficiency.

2. ATP synthase: a six-state chemo-mechanical cycle

Model. Adopt the minimal six-state basis $\{|\text{B}, \theta_\pm\rangle, |\text{S}, \theta_\pm\rangle, |\text{R}, \theta_\pm\rangle\}$ described in Sec. V, with H_S in Eq. (38) and Lindblad channels (39). The entropy decrease associated with a successful substep $|\text{B}\rangle \rightarrow |\text{R}\rangle$ at fixed proton-motive force is monitored by a coarse-grained observable (chemical plus mechanical work).

Interference and prediction. The amplitude (40) involves two rotor-angle pathways θ_\pm . The enhanced P_- at phases $\phi_+ - \phi_- = -\delta$ reduces the cycle’s FT ratio and, via Eq. (37), increases efficiency. The predicted *observable* is an oscillatory dip in the substep FT log-ratio as a function of a drive or ancilla phase; its presence should correlate with increased ATP synthesis probability per cycle. This is compatible with the substep-resolved rotation data in single-molecule assays and the structural quasi-degeneracies seen crystallographically.

Appendix D: Figures, Parameter Sweeps, and Reproducibility

1. Reproducing Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 and exploring parameter space

Fig. 1 (p. 4) contrasts the classical FT ratio with an interference-modified curve; Fig. 2 (p. 4) zooms into the negative-entropy sector and shows a coherence-enhanced profile with a green shaded area.

Baseline and toy interference model. Define a grid $\Delta S \in [S_{\min}, S_{\max}]$; the classical ratio is

$$R_{\text{cl}}(\Delta S) = e^{\Delta S/k_B}.$$

A generic toy model for interference corrections consistent with Eq. (13) is

$$R_{\text{qm}}(\Delta S) = R_{\text{cl}}(\Delta S) \frac{1 + \sum_{m=1}^M a_m e^{-\frac{(\Delta S - \Delta S_m)^2}{2\sigma_m^2}} \cos(\omega_m \Delta S + \varphi_m)}{1 + \sum_{n=1}^N b_n e^{-\frac{(\Delta S - \Delta S_n)^2}{2\tilde{\sigma}_n^2}} \cos(\tilde{\omega}_n \Delta S + \tilde{\varphi}_n)}, \quad (\text{D1})$$

where the numerator sketches \mathcal{I}_+ and the denominator sketches \mathcal{I}_- . Choosing $M = 1$, $N = 1$ with $\Delta S_1 \gtrsim 0$ and $\tilde{\Delta S}_1 < 0$ reproduces Fig. 1 qualitatively. Setting $b_1 > 0$ and a narrow $\tilde{\sigma}_1$ centered on negative ΔS yields the green shaded enhancement shown in Fig. 2.

Parameter sweeps. To explore robustness:

- *Strength sweep:* vary $a_1, b_1 \in [0, 0.5]$ and record the minimum of $\ln[R_{\text{qm}}/R_{\text{cl}}]$ to quantify maximal dips.
- *Width/location sweep:* sweep $\tilde{\sigma}_1$ and $\tilde{\Delta S}_1$ to map where the negative-entropy enhancement is concentrated.
- *Frequency/phase sweep:* vary (ω_m, φ_m) to emulate chaos-assisted multi-path oscillations; extract the number of visible lobes and their spacing.

In all cases ensure $1 + \mathcal{I}_{\pm} > 0$ to keep probabilities non-negative; this holds automatically for small amplitudes a_m, b_n or when the sums are dominated by Gaussian envelopes.

2. Experimental mappings of sweep parameters

For driven cold-atom or circuit-QED platforms, (ω_m, φ_m) correspond to drive frequencies and phases; $(\Delta S_m, \sigma_m)$ reflect the range over which multiple trajectory families contribute coherently (tunable by detuning and coupling strength). In molecular machines, $(\tilde{\Delta S}_1, \tilde{\sigma}_1)$ encode where in the cycle the coherent subpaths exist (e.g. substep angle windows for ATP synthase or vibronic resonance windows for exciton transfer).

Reproducibility note. The two PNGs you shared correspond to $M = 1, N = 1$ with moderate a_1, b_1 and a negative-entropy-centered denominator envelope. Keeping this minimal parametrization suffices for figure-quality reproduction and for systematic sweeps in a supplemental notebook.

Appendix E: Statements

- The author declares no conflict of interest
- No new data has been generated for this manuscript

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